

Fig. S1: Volcano plots and pathway analysis of the genes that were differentially expressed between the TAC and Sham groups, the NRG/TAC and Sham groups, and the NRG/TAC and sal/TAC groups.

Xu et al. 2026

Fig. S2: Heatmap illustrating the 23 genes that were differentially expressed both between the NRG/TAC and Sal/TAC groups and between the NRG/TAC and Sham groups.

Fig. S3: Intermittent NRG1 treatment via daily intraperitoneal injections improves ejection fraction after TAC. Echocardiographic measurements were performed 7 days after surgery. Data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation. Two-way ANOVA was followed by Fisher's Least Significant Difference (LSD) analysis to test treatment and surgery effects.